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PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX

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Abstract: In the context of global climate change, water resource scarcity, and demographic growth, the sustainable development of the viticulture industry and ensuring food security are among the most important economic tasks. The article analyzes the influence of factors such as vineyard area, harvested vineyard area, precipitation, average temperature, and population size on the volume of grape cultivation through econometric modeling. Correlation-regression analysis results provide forecast indicators for strategic industry planning based on a quantitative assessment of the impact of crop area growth, climatic factors, and demographic changes on production prospects. Taking into account the factors affecting the volume of grape production in the viticulture complex of Uzbekistan, in particular the area of vineyards that have begun to bear fruit, the amount of precipitation, the average annual temperature and the dynamics of the population, the forecast parameters of the volume of grape production until 2030 have been developed.

Keywords: export potential, diversification, systems approach, correlation and regression analysis, statistical calculation, empirical analysis, hypothesis, dependent and independent variables, (OLS) model, trend model, constant influence model, coefficient of determination, variance.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, two major global trends—global climate change and demographic growth—require a fundamental transformation of the viticulture industry, as well as all sectors of the agro-industrial complex. According to United Nations forecasts, the growth of the world's population requires a sharp increase in measures to ensure food security. In particular, in the context of Central Asia and Uzbekistan, the agricultural sector is not only a driver of economic stability but also a source of vital goods per capita. Viticulture is a strategic direction in our country with centuries-old historical experience and national agricultural traditions.

Changes in the volume of grape cultivation depend on many interrelated factors. On the one hand, the total area of vineyards and the area of vineyards that have entered the actual harvest directly determine the volume of cultivation, and on the other hand, climatic indicators such as average temperature and precipitation have a decisive impact on biological productivity. In addition, the growth of the total population is a demographic factor that determines both the demand in the domestic market and the labor resources in the industry.

In the context of current global economic and environmental changes, the issue of sustainable agricultural development is becoming increasingly relevant. From this perspective, viticulture should be highlighted as one of the important sectors of our republic's agriculture. This is because the cultivation and processing of grape products serve not only to improve the fodder supply in the domestic market but also to increase export potential.

In particular, the intensification of global climate change, the sharp depletion of water resources, factors threatening food security, and rising food prices on the global market further reveal the need to reform and modernize the viticulture industry. Under these conditions, one of the important tasks for the sustainable development of the industry is the provision of production processes with modern technologies and fixed assets, the use of effective financial mechanisms, and the rational and targeted use of available resources. Furthermore, increasing the economic efficiency of the viticulture sector, creating new jobs, and increasing the production of export-oriented products will contribute to the diversification of the country's agriculture, improve the living standards of the rural population, and ensure sustainable growth of the

national economy.

Within the framework of the Program for the Comprehensive Development of Viticulture and Winemaking for 2023-2026, practical work is being carried out in our country to further ensure the sustainable development of the viticulture and winemaking sector, increase and establish the cultivation of new promising industrial grape varieties, strengthen the supply of raw materials and provide financial support to processing enterprises, train qualified specialists, and increase the export volume of grape and wine products. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-260¹ dated August 3, 2023, «On measures aimed at the further development of viticulture and winemaking in 2023-2026,» also defines important tasks. The «Roadmap» defined in this resolution states the need to ensure the fulfillment of measures, as well as target and forecast indicators.

In order to ensure the development of this sector in agriculture, it will be possible to widely attract new technologies to the industry, rational use of water and land resources, reduce the impact of environmental and climate change and improve the quality of products. Therefore, it is important to continuously stimulate the cultivation of grapes and grape products through various means.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

American scientist Gregory V. Jones, a climatologist of viticulture, analyzed the world's largest viticultural regions (France, Italy, USA) and found that an increase in average annual temperature significantly accelerates the phenophases (flowering, ripening) of grapes. However, researchers have proven that extreme heat waves (thermal stress) disrupt the balance of sugar and acidity in grapes, reducing both the quality of the harvest and the overall biological volume.

Hans Reiner Schulz from Germany, studying the consequences of climate change for European viticulture, showed that a decrease in natural precipitation threatens the future of traditional rainfed and conventionally irrigated vineyards. According to the scientist's conclusion, the only way to achieve a stable harvest under changing precipitation patterns is to immediately transition to artificial and intelligent hydraulic systems such as drip irrigation.

In the research of economist Sh.A. Toshmatov, it is noted that in countries with transition economies, population growth creates a «labor surplus» in rural areas. Since viticulture requires a lot of manual labor (raw harvesting, cutting, sorting, packaging), demographic growth contributes to lower production costs by providing the industry with cheap and available labor.

In the process of studying the activities of agro-industrial and viticultural clusters, the Uzbek agricultural economist K.A. Choriev revealed a very important economic pattern. In his opinion, the main driver in increasing the gross harvest is not the «total area of vineyards,» but the dynamics of the share of «the area of vineyards that have entered the harvest.» In the first years, newly planted vineyards require only capital expenditures and do not yield an economic effect. Therefore, when modeling production volumes, it is necessary to differentially (separately) evaluate the areas of «young and unharvested» and «productive age.»

A review of available literature shows that to date, scientists have primarily studied the effects of temperature and precipitation only on plants. Economists, on the other hand, were more limited to the analysis of land areas and resources and analyzed population size and market demand in the direction of general sectors of the agricultural sector. However, considering natural-climatic (temperature, precipitation), econometric-production (area of harvested vineyards), and demographic (population) factors as a single integrated system, the issues of mathematical-econometric modeling of their combined, synergistic influence on the volume of grape production have not been studied. Especially in the context of intensifying climatic risks and water scarcity, forecasting the prospects of viticulture based on these 5 factors for Uzbekistan, where the population is growing, through multifactorial regression analysis determines the main scientific novelty of our research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a systems approach, statistical analysis, correlation, and multi-factor linear regression analysis (Multiple Linear Regression). The model of the dependence of grape production volume (Y) on the selected factors is as follows:

$$Y_i = \alpha_i + \beta_1 x_{k,i} + \dots + \beta_5 x_{k,i} + u_i \quad (3.1)$$

Here,

Y_i – dependent variable, the volume of grape cultivation in our model;

¹ <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7558039>

X_k – ($k=1...n$) independent variables; x_1 – area of vineyards; x_2 – area of a harvested vineyard; x_3 – precipitation; x_4 – average temperature; x_5 – total population;

$\beta_1... \beta_6$ – the coefficients of each variable, i.e., the coefficients of independent variables obtained from regression results; u_i – standard error.

The econometric analysis of these data was based on the fourteen-year data of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this case, variables such as the volume of grape cultivation (Y) were selected as the primary dependent variable, and the area of vineyards (X1), the area of harvested vineyards (X2), the amount of precipitation (X3), average temperature (X4), and the total population (X5) were selected as independent variables, and analysis was conducted using these variables.

In the dissertation work, the following linear model was developed using the OLS (least squares method) model within the framework of the research goals and objectives, as well as to substantiate their scientific and methodological solutions, using existing data.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Taking into account the volume of grape cultivation in the republic in 2010-2023 and the factors (variables) affecting it, we attempted to develop forecast indicators for grape cultivation until 2030. Taking into account the aforementioned indicators and other key indicators, we attempted to develop the relationship between the volume of grape cultivation in 2010-2023 and the factors influencing it using econometric methods (models) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Factors selected for econometric analysis²

As can be seen from Figure 1 above, factors such as the volume of grape cultivation, the area of vineyards, the area of harvested vineyards, precipitation, average temperature, and the total population were selected as the primary indicators for econometric analysis (Table 1).

Table 1.
Volume of grape production in the republic for 2010-2023³

Years	Volume of grape production, thousand tons	Area of vineyards, thousand ha	Area of harvested vineyards, thousand hectares	Precipitation rate mm	Medium temperature S ^o	Total population, thousand people
2010	987.3	127.9	108.7	231	15.6	29123.4
2011	1072.1	127.1	111.5	248.4	15	29555.4
2012	1179.9	126.9	111.1	216.9	14.6	29993.5
2013	1294	127.8	113.8	229.5	15.6	30492.8
2014	1397	128.9	119.4	246.2	14.3	31022.5
2015	1518.2	128.3	118.7	270.9	15.6	31575.3
2016	1613.1	131.2	122.4	281.2	16.1	32120.5
2017	1625.5	114.5	103.6	251	15.3	32656.7
2018	1589.8	113.3	100.9	196.5	15.3	33255.5
2019	1603.3	120.2	104.5	238.3	15.6	33905.2
2020	1606.9	128.2	105.7	240.2	15	34558.9
2021	1695.3	133.7	109.6	230	15.9	35271.3

² Prepared by the author based on literature.

³ Prepared based on data from the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2022	1760.6	136.8	113.1	234.5	15.4	36024.9
2023	1737.6	139.4	117.6	242.3	15.1	36799.8

In the process of analyzing these selected indicators, final conclusions are drawn, taking into account the most statistically significant variables.

At the same time, data on the volume of grape cultivation and the factors influencing it, as well as data using the «statistical calculation» method, were revised. The statistical description of the data used for the empirical analysis is presented in Table 2 (Table 2).

Table 2. Statistical description of the data used in the analyses⁴

Variables	Unit of measurement	Medium	Standard deviation	Min.	Max.
Resultant (independent) variable:					
Volume of grape cultivation	ton	1141.75	458.75	401.5	1760.6
Influencing (independent) variables:					
Area of vineyards	gektar	124.74	6.69	113.3	139.4
Fruit-bearing vineyard area	gektar	106.93	7.55	96.8	122.4
Precipitation rate	mm	235.69	17.49	196.5	281.2
Average temperature	S ⁰	15.37	0.54	14.3	16.2
Jami aholi soni	kishi	29959.36	3744.58	24813.1	36799.8

From the indicators in Table 2 above, we can conclude that while the volume of grape cultivation is taken as the dependent variable, all other variables are independent. From 2010 to 2023, the average volume of grape cultivation in our republic amounted to 1,141.75 thousand tons. At the same time, we can see that during these years, the area of vineyards grown with grapes increased by more than 124 thousand hectares, and the area of vineyards that have begun to produce grapes amounted to 106 thousand hectares. Variables (factors) such as precipitation and average temperature were also used to increase the accuracy of these analyses.

The sequence in which econometric modeling is performed is considered one of the important stages in the scientific and methodological analysis of the topics selected in the research work. In this case, the topics are first studied in depth from the perspective of economic theory, and a mathematical model of the topic is selected based on the studied economic theory. Here, based on the specifics of the topic under study, an econometric model is selected and data is collected to determine which of the production functions is appropriate (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Stages of econometric modeling

After evaluating the data using an econometric model, the compliance of scientific hypotheses (hypotheses) with the model is verified. Only after this are forecasting operations performed, practical recommendations are developed based on the final results, and the conducted studies are primarily subjected to regression analysis. The main goal of regression analysis is to evaluate the functional dependence of the conditional average value of the resulting variable on the variable characteristics⁵.

⁴ Results of calculations performed by the author in the Stata 15 program.

⁵ Berkinov B.B. Econometrics: a study guide. – T.: "Science and Technology," 2015, p. 184. Berkinov B.B.

When analyzing the volume of grape production in the republic for 2010-2023, it is important to study the direct influence of various factors. For this purpose, we aimed to use a linear econometric model widely used by economists. Researchers have extensively used this method to solve their research questions, and in many cases, they used a «constant effect» model based on the Cobb-Douglas function when analyzing the data. In their model, the dependent and independent variables are given in logarithmic form. Also, Kumbhakar et al. have described the issues of using the «constant effect» model based on the Cobb-Douglas function in their work.

Based on the above literature, in our research work, we evaluated the effects between variables using a logarithmic (logarithmed to reduce the size of some of the provided indicators and simplify elasticity calculations) and linear «least squares method» (OLS) models. The relationships between the given variables were analyzed using the Stata-17 program based on the data described above.

In the figures below, the data can be viewed as correspondence to the model and as an explanation; Figure 3 shows a two-way scatter diagram showing a positive correlation between the volume of grape cultivation and the area of vineyards entering the harvest. Here, the closer the points are to the line, the closer the relationship will be. Points lagging behind are errors that have accumulated due to various factors in production (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

Correlation between the volume of grape cultivation and the acreage of harvested vineyards⁶

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be stated that the variables selected for the model are statistically significant and have a positive effect (see Table 2). In particular, it has been scientifically substantiated that a one percent increase in the area of harvested vineyards can lead to a decrease in grape production by an average of 21,8 percent, while a one percent increase in precipitation leads to a decrease in grape production by an average of 0,8 percent. At the same time, we can see that other variables used in the model are also statistically significant and have a positive impact. Also, the value of the R-square in the model ($R=0,97$) shows how correct the model is (Table 2).

⁶ Author's development based on the Stata-17 program.

Table 2.
Description of results obtained based on the least squares method model⁷

Variables	Coefficients	Standard error	t-value
Area of vineyards	19.2***	3.51	5.49
Fruit-bearing vineyard area	21.8***	3.95	5.52
Precipitation rate	-0.87	1.12	-3.21
Average temperature	0.71*	0.27	0.75
Total population	0.11***	0.04	0.12
Constant value	31.4***	41.7	6.5
R-square	0.97		

Note: ***, **, * Express the statistical significance of the results at levels of 1, 5, and 10%. We also attempted to develop forecast indicators for 2024-2030 based on this indicator using variables such as the volume of grape cultivation and the area of vineyards for the period 2010-2023, as presented in the dissertation. When developing these forecast parameters, the Trend model was developed using the Stata-17 program.

We know that various methods are used in the development of forecasting models. In this research work, we developed a forecast function based on data from the last 14 years. In our research work, a linear function was used to develop the forecast function.

- (1) Linear function for forecasting the volume of grape production:
 $y = 44,731x + 874,1$ $R^2 = 0,91$
- (2) Linear forecasting function of the total area of vineyards (Figure 4):
 $y = 19,742x + 336,7$ $R^2 = 0,66$

Where,
y – resultant sign
x – variable sign
 R^2 – coefficient of determination

Figure 4. Forecast indicators of grape production volumes until 2030⁸

⁷ Results of calculations performed by the author in the Stata 15 program.

⁸ Results of calculations performed by the author in the Stata 17 program.

From the given function, we can see that the values of the R square are 0,91 and 0,66, respectively; that is, the values of the functions correspond to the model data set selected for these analyses.

R square is a statistical measure that represents the ratio of the variance of the dependent variable represented by the independent variables or variables in a regression model. R square tells us how much the variance of one variable represents the variance of the other. If the calculated R-square value is greater than 0.50, it means that almost half of the analyzed variations can be represented in the model based on the selected factors. In forecasting, the linear increase in the volume of grape cultivation and the area of vineyards was scientifically substantiated.

The analysis showed that under the influence of these variables, the volume of grape production in the republic may increase from an average of 987.3 thousand tons in 2010 to 2034.3 thousand tons by 2030, or 2.1 times. At the same time, it is scientifically substantiated that the area of vineyards where grapes are grown can reach 159.4 thousand hectares by 2030, according to the forecast results.

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